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ASSESSMENT OF THE DEGREE OF PRESERVATION OF CORONARY RESERVES IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH MITRAL STENOSIS.....11
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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE CONDITION OF WOMEN DURING CESAREAN SECTION UNDER SPINAL ANESTHESIA AND MEDICAL SEDATION.....16
3. **Khudoyberdieva Gulrukh Sobirovna, Matlubov Mansur Muratovich**
SEDATION AND PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL STATUS OF WOMEN IN REGIONAL ANESTHESIA FOR CAESAREAN SECTION. CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM.....24
4. **Sharipov Isroil Latipovich**
HEMODYNAMIC GRADATIONS DURING COMBINED USAGE OF EXTRACORPORAL DETOXIFICATION METHODS IN CHILDREN WITH RENAL FAILURE.....31
5. **Pardaev Shukur Kuylievich, Sharipov Isroil Latipovich**
APPLICATION OF CENTRAL NEURAXIAL ANESTHESIA IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF LUMBAR-SACRAL DISC HERNIATIONS.....38
6. **Yusupov Jasur Tolibovich, Matlubov Mansur Muratovich**
ENHANCING INTENSIVE CARE FOR PATIENTS FOLLOWING CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING (LITERATURE REVIEW).....44

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7. **Ahmedova Aziza Tayirovna, Rasulova Feruza Golibovna**
ASSESSMENT OF PERINATAL COMPLICATIONS RISK USING REMOTE CARDIOTOCOGRAPHY MONITORING.....52
8. **Agababyan Larisa Rubenovna, Usmankulova Habiba Mizrobjonovna**
NEW TREATMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME.....59
9. **Nasirova Zebiniso Azizovna**
APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ANEMIA IN HEAVY MENSTRUAL BLEEDING.....66
10. **Zakirova Nodira Islomovna, Yuldasheva Farangiz Ismatilloevna**
CORRECTION AND TACTICS OF PREGNANCY ADMINISTRATION IN CASE OF VIOLATIONS OF THE VAGINAL ECOSYSTEM.....76

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

11. **Orzikulov Azam Orzikulovich, Haydarov Akbar Haydarovich**
ANTIVIRAL THERAPY IN VIRAL HEPATITIS “C” DISEASE EFFICIENCY (A CASE FROM PRACTICE).....80
12. **Oslanov Absamat Abdurakhimovich, Soibnazarov Orzukul Ernazarovich**
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE VIRAL LOAD TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF LIVER FIBROSIS IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS «B» (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAMARKAND REGION).....86
13. **Kadirov Zhonibek Fayzullayevich, Rizaev Jasur Alimdjanovich, Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdiyevich**
MOLECULAR MECHANISMS OF IMMUNOLOGICAL ACTIVATION IN HIV INFECTION.....92

ENDOCRINOLOGY

14. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Rasulov Jamshedjon Shavkatovich**
EFFICACY OF FOLK REMEDIES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS AT RISK OF STROKE.....106
15. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Ergashev Asadullo Ubaydullo o'g'li**
THE IMPORTANCE OF BLOOD RHEOLOGY IN DIABETES IN THE ORIGIN OF ISCHEMIC STROKE AND THE EFFECT OF HIRUDOTHERAPY ON BLOOD RHEOLOGY.....111
16. **Fozilova Umida Kamalovna, Khabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
THE ROLE OF GLYCEMIC CONTROL IN PREVENTING DENTAL COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES(REVIEW ARTICLE).....116
17. **Saidova Shakhnoza Aripovna, Yakubov Abdusalol Vahobovich, Pulatova Durдона Baxadirovna**
THE EFFECT OF GLP-1 RECEPTOR AGONISM ON DIVERSE ASPECTS OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES AND OBESITY.....122

MORPHOLOGY

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE GALLBLADDER WALL IN EXPERIMENTAL CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS.....128
19. **M.A. Abdullayeva, O.O. Zaripova.**
DETERMINATION OF THE ACCUMULATION LEVEL OF ARTIFICIAL FOOD COLORANTS E 171 AND E 173 IN THE BRAIN.....135
20. **Mamataliyev Abdumalik Rasulovich**
ANATOMICAL AND TOPOGRAPHICAL STRUCTURE OF THE EXTRAHEPATIC BILE DUCT IN EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS.....140
21. **Ismailov Jasur Mardonovich**
ABOUT BRONCHIECTASIS AS A TYPE OF CHRONIC NONSPECIFIC LUNG DISEASE.....144
22. **Ismailov Jasur Mardonovich, Norjigitov Azamat Musokulovich**
MORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF BRONCHI AND LUNG TISSUES IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIECTASIS.....150
23. **Juraev Kamoliddin Danabaevich, Islamov Shavkat Erjigitovich**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE THYMUS IN NEWBORNS IN THE LATE NEONATAL PERIOD.....158
24. **Rakhimova Gulnoz Shamsievna, Teshayev Shuxrat Jumayevich.**
ASSESSMENT OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE TESTES ON THE FIRST DAY AFTER ACUTE TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY.....168

NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY

25. **Ruzmetova Saodat Umarjonovna**
FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EARLY POSTNATAL HEALTH IN CHILDREN WHO HAVE SUFFERED PERINATAL CNS DAMAGE.....173
26. **Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadullaevna, Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna, Abruev Khudoerkhon Oybekovich**
CLINICAL FEATURES OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE IN THYROID HOMEOSTASIS DISRUPTION.....178

27. **Adambaev Zufar Ibragimovich, Kilichev Ibodullo Abdullayevich, Samiyev Asliddin Sayitovich, Khudoyberganov Nurmamat Yusupovich, Pazilova Aida Sultanovna**
CORRECTION OF COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENTS IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL ISCHEMIA IN OUTPATIENT SETTINGS.....185
28. **Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadulloevna, Nurboeva Iroda Samariddin Qizi**
PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....192
29. **Khamdamova Bakhora Komiljonovna, Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich, Muhammadiyeva Dilafruz Po'lot qizi**
INNOVATIVE METHODS OF THERAPY FOR NEUROVASCULAR DISORDERS IN LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHIES.....202
30. **Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna, Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadulloevna**
DANCE MOVEMENT REHABILITATION TO REDUCE COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH EARLY-ONSET PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....209
31. **Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich, Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadulloevna, Zoxidjonova Shahnoza Zoxidjonovna**
FEATURES OF PSYCHOPATHOLOGICAL AND AUTONOMIC DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PAIN SYNDROME WITH RADICULOPATHIES.....216
32. **Ergasheva Munisa Yakubovna.**
IMPROVING MEASURES FOR REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES DUE TO NERVOUS SYSTEM DISEASES.....222
33. **Raimova Malika Mukhamedjanovna, Yodgarova Umida Gaybulloyevna**
IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS BY STUDYING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RESTLESS LEGS SYNDROME AND HYPOTHYROIDISM.....229

UROLOGY

34. **Allazov Iskandar Salax Ugli, Allazov Salax Allazovich, Ablyatifov Aziz Baxtiyarovich**
OUTPATIENT UROLOGICAL-POLICLINICAL CARE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....235
35. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich, Allazov Iskandar Salakh Ogli, Ergashev Arslonbek Shuxratjon Ogli**
MEDICAL-SOCIAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF UROLOGICAL DISEASES. LITERATURE REVIEW.....242
36. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich, Batirov Bekhzod Amindjanovich.**
DISTRIBUTION OF UROLOGICAL DISEASES AND METHODS FOR THEIR DETECTION PHARMACOLOGY AND TRADITIONAL MEDICINE.....247
37. **Mirrakhimova Maktuba Habibullaevna, Nishanbaeva Nilufar Yunusjanovna**
FILAGGRIN DEFECT IN ATOPIC DERMATITIS AND MODERN METHODS OF CORRECTION.....256
38. **Egamova Malika Tursunovna, Rasulov Jamshedjon Shavkatovich.**
HIRUDOTHERAPY, THE EFFECT OF VARIOUS TREATMENT METHODS.....262

PEDIATRICS AND PEDIATRIC SURGERY

39. **Abdullaev Zafar Bobirovich, Agzamkhodjaev Saidanvar Talatovich**
ANTENATAL DIAGNOSTICS OF BLADDER EXTROPHY: CONTEMPORARY POSSIBILITIES AND PROSPECTS.....267
40. **Rakhimova Durdona Zhurakulovna**
HYGIENIC ASSESSMENT OF ACTUAL NUTRITION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN.....274

41. **Ganiev Abdurashid Ganievich, Sanakulov Abdulatif Burkhanovich**
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE FAMILY OF A SICK CHILD.....284
42. **Naimushina Elena Serafimovna, Kilina Alla Vladimirovna, Chervinskih Tatyana Anatolyevna**
GENDER-SPECIFIC CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF OBESITY IN ADOLESCENTS.....293
43. **Nuritdinova Gavhar Taipovna, Inakova Barno Bahodirovna, Abduvahobova Gulmira, Arzibekova Umida Abdukodirovna.**
DELAYED NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN NEWBORNS WITH MODERATE AND SEVERE ASPHYXIA.....299
44. **Ollabergenov Odilbek, Baratov Feruz**
MINIMALLY INVASIVE INTERVENTIONS IN ACUTE PLEURAL EMPYEMA IN CHILDREN.....305

ONCOLOGY

45. **Ulmasov Firdavs Gayratovich, Esankulova Bustonoy Sobirovna.**
THE ROLE OF VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR (VEGF) IN OVARIAN CANCER WITH PERITONEAL CARCINOMATOSIS IN STAGES III AND IV.....311
46. **Kahharov Alisher, Khodjayeva Nozima**
THE IMPACT OF FERTILITY PRESERVATION PROGRAMS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF WOMEN WITH ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES.....318
47. **Zaripova Parvina Ilkhomovna, Yorov Lutfillo Shukurulloevich, Kutlumurotov Otabek Bekjanovich, Juraev Mirjalol Dehkonovich**
ABOUT THE PROBLEM OF BREAST CANCER RECURRENCE CAUSES.....323

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

48. **Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Gaibullaev Elbek Azizbekovich, Akramova Nozima Akramovna, Pustovetova Maria Genadievna**
ANALYSIS OF CYTOKINE PROFILE IN GINGIVAL CREVICULAR FLUID OF PATIENTS WITH AGGRESSIVE PERIODONTITIS: PATHOGENETIC AND DIAGNOSTIC ASPECTS.....333
49. **Daminova Nargiza Ravshanovna, Makhkamova Oqila Abdushukurovna, Sadikova Dilfuza Ravshanbekovna, Inogamov Sherzod Muhamatisakovich**
EVALUATION OF THE IMMUNOLOGICAL AND RESPIRATORY STATUS OF PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA WITH COMORBID PATHOLOGY OF THE ORAL CAVITY.....338
50. **Axmedov Xurshid Kamalovich**
ASSESSMENT OF STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN PERIODONTAL TISSUES DURING PROSTHETICS WITH METAL-CERAMIC AND ZIRCONIUM DENTURES.....344
51. **Olimova Dildora Vohid qizi**
DENTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH END-STAGE CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE (A STUDY OF PATIENTS RECEIVING AND NOT RECEIVING HEMODIALYSIS).352
52. **Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich, Mardonova Dildora Kasimovna**
IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR HYPERTROPHIC GINGIVITIS IN PATIENTS WITH EPILEPSY.....358

53. **Khotamova Madina Anvarovna, Odiljonova Mukhimaoy Savlatovna**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF PERIODONTITIS AND THE ORGANIZATION OF DENTAL MEASURES FOR WORKERS OF METAL PROCESSING ENTERPRISES.....366
54. **Umarova Makhfuza Usmanovna**
THE IMPACT OF CHRONIC USE OF NICOTINE-CONTAINING PRODUCTS ON THE PROGRESSION OF INFLAMMATORY-DYSTROPHIC DISEASES OF THE ORAL CAVITY: CLINICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS.....370
55. **Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich, Allazarov Kuvondik Azadovich**
IMPROVING THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTRODUODENITIS.....377
56. **Allazarov Kuvondik Azadovich, Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich.**
USE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF OZONE IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GASTRODUODENITIS385
57. **Mardonova Dildora Kasimovna, Zoyirov Tulkin Elnazarovich**
OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS FOR EXAMINING PERIODONT TISSUE DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH EPILEPSY393
58. **Akhmedov Ilhom Ibrohimovich, Kamalova Feruza Raxmatullaeva.**
CHANGES IN MICROFLORA NON-SPECIFIC FACTORS PROTECTION OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN CHILDREN WITH INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF MAXILLOFACIAL.....401
59. **Yuldashev Forrukh Farkhod Ugli, Kuryazov Akbar Kuranboevich, Khabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES AND APPROACHES TO THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF DENTAL DISEASES IN DEAF-MUTE CHILDREN (REVIEW ARTICLE).....406
60. **Navruzova Ugilxon Orzijon Qizi, Xabibova Nazira Nasulloevna.**
THE ROLE OF IMMUNE STATUS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS.....414
61. **Tojiyev Feruz Ibodulla ugli, Beysenbayev Nurbek Kunanbay ugli, Ismoilkhojaeva Komila G'ani qizi.**
RECONSTRUCTION OF MANDIBULAR DEFECTS IN CHILDREN WITH INDIVIDUALLY MANUFACTURED TITANIUM IMPLANTS AFTER REMOVAL OF BENIGN TUMORS.....419

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

62. **Giyasov Zaynitdin Asamutdinovich, Gulyamov Dilshod Erkinovich**
FORENSIC ASSESSMENT OF INJURIES TO MAJOR JOINTS IN ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS.....425

THERAPY AND INTERNAL MEDICINE

63. **Tashkenbayeva Eleonora Negmatovna, Esankulov Mukhammad Olimovich**
SIGNIFICANCE OF UROMODULIN IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....431

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

64. **Abrolov Hakimjon Kobiljonovich, Xolmurotov Akmal Abdumalikovich, Irisov Ortikali Tulaevich, Berdiev Kobiljon Bahromovich, Rakhimberganov Khusanboy Davlatnazarovich**
NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ASCENDING AORTIC ANEURYSM.....437

65. **Ashirov Mavlon Umirzakovitch.**
BIOMECHANICAL INSIGHTS INTO MDICO FOR FLATFOOT CORRECTION.....445
66. **Khodjanov Iskandar Yunusovich, Ubaydullaev Sherozbek Farkhodovich**
IMPROVING THE METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF VALGOUS DEFORMATION OF THE ELBOW JOINT.....459
67. **Mamasoliev Bakhodir Mamausupovich**
FEATURES OF THROMBOEMBOLIC COMPLICATIONS PREVENTION DURING SURGICAL TREATMENT OF KNEE JOINT DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LOWER LIMB VENOUS DISEASE.....468
68. **Melibayev Salimjon Tashtanovich, Karshiboyev Abduvakhob Jamboyevich, Nomazov Olim Ergash Og'Li, Jurayev Ilhom G'ulomovich**
VERTEBRAL COMPRESSION FRACTURES: CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS, AND MODERN TREATMENT STRATEGIES.....475
69. **Karshiboyev Abduvakhob Jamboyevich, Melibayev Salimjon Tashtanovich, Nomazov Olim Ergash Og'Li, Jalilov Khusan Mukhitdinovich.**
HIP FRACTURE, DIAGNOSIS, SURGICAL TREATMENT, REHABILITATION, THROMBOEMBOLIC PROPHYLAXIS, BISPHTHONATES, FALL PREVENTION.....489
70. **Kholkhudjayev Farrukh Ikramovich**
RESULTS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ROTATOR CUFF INJURIES OF THE SHOULDER JOINT.....502
71. **Tilyakov Xasan Azizovich, Temurov Alisher Akmaljon O'g'li, Xursanov Muxriddin Xusniddin O'g'li, Yusupov Sohijon Saitxon O'g'li, Tolmasov Mirjalol Mirzohid O'g'li.**
RESULTS OF THE APPLICATION OF ADVANCED OSTEOSYNTHESIS IN DIAPHYSEAL FRACTURES OF THE HUMERUS.....508

RADIATION IMAGING

72. **Ikramova Zulfiya Tulkinovna, Rozikhodjaeva Gulnora Ahmedovna, Soipova Guzal Gulomidinovna**
ASSESSMENT OF TOTAL CEREBRAL BLOOD FLOW IN PATIENTS WITH CAROTIC ATHEROSCLEROSIS.....515

SURGERY

73. **Akhmedov Adkham Ibadullaevich, Fayazov Abdulaziz Djalilovich**
PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF MOTOR-EVACUATION DYSFUNCTION OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT IN SEVERELY BURNED PATIENTS.....523
74. **Sayinaev Farrukh Karamatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich**
LAPAROSCOPIC AND OPEN HERNIOPLASTY FOR VENTRAL HERNIAS: SURGICAL OUTCOMES AND COMPLICATIONS ASSESSMENT.....532
75. **Daminov Feruz Asatullaevich, Shomurodov Khabibullo Abdumalik Ugli, Rakhmonov Kosim Erdanovich.**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TACTICS IN ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE CHOLECYSTITIS: THE ROLE OF LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY AND RISK FACTOR ANALYSIS.....539
76. **Khayitov Laziz Milionerovich, Khakimov Erkin Abdikhalilovich, Zuvaytov Shoxrux G'ayrat o'g'li, Abrorov Shahbozjon Nematzoda**
THE ROLE ENDOBRONCHIAL COMPLEX THERAPY AT PATIENTS WITH THE INHALATION TRAUMA.....544

OPHTHALMOLOGY

77. **Fayzieva Dilorom Buritoshevna, Akhmedova Dilafruz Baxadirovna, Mirzaev Dilshodbek Akhmedovich.**
VISUAL DISORDERS AND THEIR IMPACT ON PERIPHERAL VISION AND EYE MOVEMENT COORDINATION.....549

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FEATURES OF PSYCHOPATHOLOGICAL AND AUTONOMIC DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PAIN SYNDROME WITH RADICULOPATHIES

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: To study the features of psychopathological and vegetative disorders in 82 patients with chronic pain syndrome in dorsopathy of compression-ischemic origin.

Methods: In patients with chronic pain syndrome with dorsopathy of compression-ischemic origin, the psychological and vegetative state was studied using questionnaires and scales.

Results: In groups of patients with radiculopathy, using psychological scales, the state of asthenia, anxiety and vegetative changes was studied. The research conducted using the Spielberg-Khanin scales of reactive and personal anxiety revealed a rather high level of anxiety. Particularly significant was the detection of mild and moderate depression on the Beck scale. The results of the Kerdo index indicated damage to the autonomic nervous system in all patients, with a predominance of parasympathicotonic manifestations.

Conclusions. The use of these techniques helps to identify conditions associated with chronic pain syndrome such as anxiety, asthenia, depression, etc., with the possibility of studying the dynamics of the patients' well-being. These patients with severe psycho-emotional disorders need a more thorough clinical examination, consultations of appropriate specialists and treatment.

Key words: Radiculopathy, scales of personal anxiety, depression, autonomic dystonia syndrome.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПСИХОПАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ВЕГЕТАТИВНЫХ РАССТРОЙСТВ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ХРОНИЧЕСКИМ БОЛЕВЫМ СИНДРОМОМ ПРИ РАДИКУЛОПАТИЯХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель: Изучить особенности психопатологических и вегетативных нарушений у 82 больных с хроническим болевым синдромом при дорсопатии компрессионно-ишемического генеза.

Методы: У больных с хроническим болевым синдромом при дорсопатии компрессионно-ишемического генеза проводились исследования психологического и вегетативного состояния при помощи анкет и шкал.

Полученные результаты: В группах пациентов с радикулопатиями с помощью психологических шкал было исследовано состояние астении, тревожности и вегетативных изменений. Проводились исследования по шкалам реактивной и личностной тревожности Спилберга-Ханина выявила достаточно высокий уровень тревожности. Результаты индекса Кердо указали на поражение вегетативной нервной системы у всех больных, с преобладанием парасимпатикотонических проявлений.

Выводы. Применение перечисленных методик помогает выявить сопутствующие хроническому болевому синдрому такие состояния, как тревога, астения, депрессия и т.д., с возможностью изучения динамики самочувствия больных. Эти больные с выраженными психоэмоциональными нарушениями нуждаются в более тщательном клиническом обследовании, консультации соответствующих специалистов и лечении.

Ключевые слова: Радикулопатия, шкалы личностной тревожности, депрессия, синдром вегетативной дистонии.

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RADIKULOPATIYALI SURUNKALI OG'RIQ SINDROMI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA PSIXOPATOLOGIK VA VEGETATIV KASALLIKLARNING XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqsad: Siqilish-ishemik kelib chiqishi dorsopatiyasida surunkali og'riq sindromi bo'lgan 82 bemorda psixopatologik va vegetativ kasalliklarning xususiyatlarini o'rganish.

Metodlar: Siqilish-ishemik kelib chiqishi dorsopatiyasi bo'lgan surunkali og'riq sindromi bo'lgan bemorlarda psixologik va vegetativ holat anketalar va shkalalar yordamida o'rganildi.

Natijalar: Radikulopatiya bilan og'riq bemorlar guruhlarida psixologik tarozilar yordamida asteniya, tashvish va vegetativ o'zgarishlar holati o'rganildi. Spilberg-Xanin reaktiv va shaxsiy tashvish shkalasi bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar tashvishning ancha yuqori darajasini aniqladi. Bek shkalasi bo'yicha yengil va o'rtacha darajadagi depressiyaning aniqlanishi ayniqsa ahamiyatlidir. Kerdo indeksining natijalari barcha bemorlarda parasimpatikotonik ko'rinishlarning ustunligi bilan avtonom nerv tizimining zararlanishini ko'rsatdi.

Xulosa. Ushbu usullardan foydalanish bemorlarning farovonligi dinamikasini o'rganish imkoniyati bilan surunkali og'riq sindromi, masalan, tashvish, asteniya, depressiya va boshqalar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan sharoitlarni aniqlashga yordam beradi. Og'ir psixo-emotsional buzilishlari bo'lgan ushbu bemorlarga batafsilroq klinik tekshiruv, tegishli mutaxassislarining maslahati va davolanish kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: Radikulopatiya, shaxsiy tashvish shkalasi, depressiya, vegetativ distoniya sindromi.

Dolzarlighi. Surunkali og'riq sindromi jiddiy tibbiy muammodir, chunki u bemorning hayot sifatiga, uning mehnat qobiliyatiga va jismoniy salomatligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Radikulopatiyada surunkali og'riq paydo bo'lishida psixologik omillar juda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Astenik sindrom uzoq davom etgan og'riq sindromi natijasida rivojlanadi va asosiy kasallikning tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Tashvishlanish yoki tashvish sindromi o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish va o'z-o'zini tarbiyalashning tarkibiy qismi sifatida maqbul va kerakli bo'lganda foydali bo'lishi mumkin. Agar odamda vaziyat nisbatan yetarli darajada tashvish bo'lmasa va bu unga tahdid soladigan bo'lib tuyulsa, biz patologik shaxsiy tashvish haqida gapirishimiz mumkin.

Depressiya - bu odamning holatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan holat bo'lib, u g'amgin, tushkunlik va faoliyatiga qiziqishni yo'qotishi, ishtahaning o'zgarishi, doimiy aybdorlik va o'lim haqida o'ylaydi.

Biz surunkali og'riq sindromi bo'lgan 82 bemorni tekshirdik, ulardan 46 (56,1%) ayollar va 36 erkaklar (43,9%).

Rasm 1. Bemorlarning jinsi bo'yicha taqsimlanishi

Bemorning shikoyatlari asosida astenik sindrom namoyon bo'ldi. Bemorlarda tashvishlanish darajasi (reaktiv shkala bo'yicha vaziyatli tashvish) aniqlandi. Bemorlarga tashvish darajasi baholandi (reaktiv va shaxsiy tashvish shkalasi Spilberg-Xanin buyicha). Depressiya mavjudligi Bek Depressiya shkalasi bo'yicha aniqlandi, u 21 toifadagi simptomlar va shikoyatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Depressiyaning o'ziga xos ko'rinishlariga mos keladigan "ha" yoki "yo'q" 4-5 ta bayonotni tashkil etadi. O'tgan oxirgi hafta davomida bemorlarning sog'lig'i holati tahlil qilindi.

Asosiy psixopatologik shikoyatlar asteniya shaklida bo'lgan: umumiy kuchsizlik - 58 (70,7%); charchashlarning kuchayishi - 41 (50%); mehnat qobiliyatining pasayishi - 47 (57,3%), uyquning yomonlashishi - 51 (62,2%).

Rasm 1. Bemorlarning asosiy psixopatologik shikoyatlari

Barcha 82 (100%) bemorlarda o'tkazilgan Spilberg-Xanin tashvish shkalasi yordamida affektiv buzilishlarni tahlil qilishda o'rtacha qiymat ST uchun $31,8 \pm 8,2$ ball va LT uchun $31,5 \pm 8,1$ ballni ko'rsatdi. Olingan ma'lumotlar uzoq muddatli surunkali og'riq sindromining mavjudligi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan o'rtacha tashvish buzilishining mavjudligini ko'rsatdi, ko'pchilik bemorlarda surunkali og'riq depressiv tajribaga olib keldi, uni o'rganish uchun Bek Depressiya shkalasi ishlatilgan.

Natijalar quyidagilarni ko'rsatdi: 67 (81,7%) bemorlarda depressiya belgilari yo'q edi; 14 (17,1%) bemorda yengil tushkunlik, 1 (1,2%) bemorda o'rtacha depressiya bo'lgan. Ushbu guruhdagi bemorlarda VNSdagi o'zgarishlar kuzatildi, ular Kerdo indeksining hisob-kitoblari yordamida tahlil qilindi. Ushbu indeks quyidagicha hisoblangan: $VI = (1 - D / YUT) * 100$; bu erda VI - vegetativ indeks, D - distolik bosimning qiymati; YUT - yurak urish tezligi 1 daqiqada (to'liq vegetativ muvozanat bilan - yurak-qon tomir tizimida eytoniya VI = 0). Agar bemor uchun hisoblangan koeffitsient ijobiy bo'lsa, unda simpatik ta'sirlar ustunlik qiladi; agar koeffitsientning raqamli qiymati minus belgisi bilan olingan bo'lsa, unda bu holda parasimpatik tonus ortadi. Olingan ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, evtoniya, ya'ni vegetativ muvozanat faqat uchta (3,7%) bemorda aniqlangan, simpatik ta'sirning ustunligi 48 (58,5%), parasimpatik - 31 (37,8%) bemorlarda kuzatilgan.

Rasm 3. Bemorlarning vegetativ muvozanati

Olingan ma'lumotlar vegetativ distoniya sindromi mavjudligini ko'rsatadi, uning ta'rifi uchun biz vegetativ o'zgarishlar belgilarini aniqlaydigan so'rovnomadan foydalandik (Wayne A.M., 1998).

Bemorlarga savollar ro'yxati berildi, unga ko'ra ularning hozirgi holatiga mos keladigan "Ha" yoki "Yo'q" javobini tanlash kerak edi.

Anketa natijalari quyidagicha edi: yuzning qizarishi tendensiyasi - 0, ya'ni bu guruh bemorlarida kuzatilmadi; kuchli og'riq bilan yuzning oqarishi kuzatildi - 12 (14,6%). Savolga: sizda karaxtlik yoki sovqotish bormi: barmoqlarda, oyoqlarda 21 (25,6%) bemor ijobiy javob berdi; hech kim qo'l va oyoqlarda to'liq karaxtlikni qayd etmadi. Ba'zi bemorlarda (oqarish, qizarish, ko'karish) aniqlandi: qo'l barmoqlari, to'piqda -18 (21,9%); bemorlarda to'liq qo'l barmoqlari va to'piqlarda aniqlanmadi. Ko'p terlash simptomi ko'pchilik bemorlarda kuzatildi va 79 (96,3%) ni tashkil etdi; va "doimiy" bo'lgan terlashlar - 44 (53,6%) bemorlarda va hayajonlangan paytda - 35 (42,7%). Bemorlarning ushbu guruhida yurak urishi, "so'nishi", "yurak urishi to'xtashi" kabi holatlarning tuyilishi kuzatilmagan. Kam sonli bemorlarda nafas olishda qiyinchilik hissi havo yetishmasligi hissi shaklida aniqlangan - 9 (11%), tez nafas olish - 14 (17,5%), hayajon paytida kuzatilgan - 4 (4,9%), dim bo'lgan xonada - 10 (12%). Oshqozon-ichak traktining organlari funksiyasining buzilishi juda kam uchraydigan belgi edi: ich qotishi tendensiyasi -13 (15,8%), diareya -7 (8,5%), qorinning dam bo'lishi -21 (25,6%), og'riq. - 2 (2,4%). Sanoqli bemorlar dim xonada hushidan ketishni qayd etdilar - 3 (3,6%), hayajon - 4 (4,9%), tik holatda uzoq vaqt qolish - 2 (2,4%) bemorlarda kuzatildi. So'rovnoma bemorlarda xurujsimon bosh og'rig'ini aniqlashga yordam berdi - 60 (73,1%), ular juda tez-tez uchraydigan shikoyatlar bo'lib, ulardan: diffuz -25 (30,1%), boshning faqat yarmi - 9 (11%), "butun bosh" - 7 (8,5%), qisuvchi - 5 (6,1%) va pulsatsiyalanuvchi 9 (11%) bosh og'riqlarni tashkil

etdi. Barcha bemorlar ish qobiliyatining pasayishi - 82 (100%) va charchoq - 82 (100%) kabi holatni his qildilar. Xuddi shu tez-tez uchraydigan holat quyidagi shaklda uyqu buzilishi edi: uxlashning qiyinligi - 51 (62,2%); tez-tez uyg'onish va yuzaki, sayoz uyqu - 39 (47,5%); uyqusizlik hissi -36 (43,9%), ertalab uyg'onganda charchoq - 48 (58,5%). Olingan barcha ma'lumotlar vegetativ distoniya sindromi mavjudligini ko'rsatdi, ular 79 (96,3%) da aniqlangan.(Rasm 4)

Rasm 4. Bemorlarning so'rov natijalari

Xulosa: Siqilish-ishemik kelib chiqishi radikulopatiyasi bilan surunkali og'riq sindromi bo'lgan bemorlarning ko'pchiligida psixopatologik va vegetativ kasalliklar kuzatildi. Psixopatologik sindromlar reaktiv va shaxsiy tashvishlanish Spilberg-Xanin va depressiya BEK shkalasi bo'yicha asteno-nevrotik, tashvishlanish va depressiya ifodalangan.

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